

FEATURES, USAGE AND FORMATION OF COGNITIVE METAPHORS

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Abstract: There have always been a huge impact of cognitive metaphors on languages and the cultures of people who use them. Despite the fact that poetic and literary usage of cognitive metaphors is common, involuntary utilization by those who would like to get their speech well-conceived, well-interpreted is even more widespread. Their primary function in any language is to help people conceive something more abstract.

Key words: Cognitive metaphors, Novelty, language acquisition, creative communication, second language

Introduction

Often abstract meaning of the word or misconception of those can lead difficulties in perception of speech, mainly this occurs amongst those learning a second language. One of the best methods that could be employed to fully understand speaker's point of view is using metaphors.

According to Mark Johnson (Metaphor, Linguistics, 2013) and Boyd .R (Metaphor thought 8: 481-532) speakers regularly use metaphors in everyday language to make a complex speech easy. Perception and comprehension of ours can be shaped by metaphors making our thoughts even more crystal clear. In a daily life metaphors take a leading role in acquisition phenomena by connecting them familiar objects.

George Lakoff ("Metaphors we live by": 1980, 47p) thinks common usage of metaphors improves our thinking and has vital benefits:

1. Novel ideas: implementation of new metaphors in the structure of older ones can possibly lead to new ideas.
2. Better framing: With the help of shifting from one metaphor to another one we can frame our ideas.

The importance of recognizing the mental representations of upper-intermediate learners in learning a foreign language is a central issue in this field. There are also various limitations of the linguistic modes that can be used to define these students' perceptions. Although, research on the subject has not been conducted on the subject, it is possible to identify the multiple modes of metaphor that can be utilized to analyze the learning experience of upper-intermediate students. The goal of this study was to identify the various mental

representations of upper level Uzbek students that can be used in analyzing the learning experience of foreign language.

Review of literature

According to various theoretical perspectives, metaphor is a type of verbal activity instead of a mental activity. They (Duffey.P, Cognitive semantics, 2020, 163-188 and Eideval.G, use of metaphors, 2020, 408-425) claim that it is a creative language device that can be used to refer to a different subject outside of the usual context. Fauconnier and Turner, in 2009, explained that the metaphor's original concept was used to make comparisons between two things. This point of view led to the majority of research studies on visual metaphors being in foreign or second languages.

Metaphors can be an effective tool for analyzing common human behaviors and experiences due to their roles in human cognition (Leite, 2020). Once researchers switched their attention from an external framework of educational practice to day-to-day classroom realities, metaphors started to gain relevance as a study instrument in the fields of applied linguistics and education (Sher and Feinman, 1995). Over the past few years, the non-linguistic applications of metaphors have drawn a lot of attention. For instance, metaphorical gestures and visual metaphors have received a great deal of research (Wang, 2015; Roth and Lawless, 2002).

To access students' and teachers' cognition, researchers have employed both metaphorical gestures and visualized metaphors (Michalle, 2006; Sher and Feinman, 1995). Researchers can build helpful, indirect features of students' and instructors' cognitions by examining their metaphors (Öztürk and Yıldırım, 2016). For Xu et al. (2022) and Hunter and Serret (2020), the metaphors that learners and instructors express, or employ may subtly reveal how they plan and scheme their learning and teaching activities and how they assign meanings to their learning experiences.

According to Lakoff, the American public political scene serves as a core conceptual metaphor for "the family." People consequently perceive political figures as playing the roles of a "strict father" and a "nurturant parent." This wish to see the nation-state behave "more like a father" or "more like a mother" gives rise to two fundamental theories of political economy.

Jane Jacobs, an urban theorist and ethicist, defined the difference between a "Guardian Ethic" and a "Trader Ethic" in less gender-driven terms. She claims that trade and guarding are two real-world actions that people should learn to use as metaphors for all future decisions. Lakoff proposes that children assign

their mothers and fathers the responsibilities of "guardian" and "trader," respectively, in a society where caring for children is the primary female job and selling in a market economy is the primary masculine duty.

Conclusion

Goal of this article was to analyze the importance of metaphors in language acquisition and investigate the literatures on it by eminent scholars and experts of English. It can be concluded that metaphors are the vital tool make language easy both to interpret and communicate, as well as convey opinions.

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